

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES BASED ON INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada chet tillarni o'rgatish va o'rganishda qo'llaniladigan Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, usullari va ularni qo'llash orqali erishiladigan natijalar haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Virtual sinflar, raqamli darsliklar, veb-saytlar, mobil ilovalar, dasturiy ta'minot, video konferentsiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассказывается об информационно-коммуникационных технологиях, используемых в преподавании и изучении иностранных языков, методах и результатах, достигаемых их применением.

Ключевые слова: Виртуальные классы, цифровые учебники, веб-сайты, мобильные приложения, программное обеспечение, видеоконференции.

Abstract: This article talks about information and communication technologies used in teaching and learning foreign languages, methods and the results achieved by their application.

Keywords: Virtual classrooms, Digital textbooks, Websites, Mobile apps, software programs, Video Conferencing.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most relevant studies of online platforms of educational resources for improving the educational process based on modern technologies is related to the transition to a new competency-based paradigm of education. Online education makes up 1.1% of the total education market in Uzbekistan [2]. The possibilities of the new system allow to solve the problems of forming the student's individual educational trajectory and additional professional training, his ability to self-organize and self-educate. The development of the digital educational space of Russia is aimed at increasing the availability of general education, the implementation of the concept of continuous education, the use of modern information and communication

technologies by educational organizations. education - all of the above is the object of interest of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is striving to increase its participation in this segment of the educational services market, which is part of the priority project implemented since 2016. Modern education, seeking to find a successful e-learning algorithm, focuses on the use of online formats as one of the educational resources of education.

Based on the current technical development of temporary information and communication technologies, linguists, as well as scientists of knowledge fields, are the object of research in learning a foreign language. Studying information and communication technologies and effective search for methodological support of electronic methods of the educational process allows to consider online education as a new source of pedagogical power. Networked learning technologies, e-learning and interactive technologies help to transform and establish educational programs at a higher level.

The use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in teaching foreign languages has revolutionized language education by providing new tools, resources, and methods to enhance learning experiences. Here are some ways ICT can be effectively utilized in teaching foreign languages:

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

1. **Online Language Learning Platforms:** There are numerous online platforms and apps specifically designed for language learning, such as Duolingo, Rosetta Stone, and Babbel. These platforms offer interactive lessons, exercises, quizzes, and games to help learners develop vocabulary, grammar, listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills.

2. **Virtual Classrooms and Video Conferencing:** Virtual classrooms and video conferencing tools, like Zoom or Google Meet, enable remote language instruction and collaboration. Teachers can conduct live lessons, interactive activities, and discussions with students from anywhere in the world, providing real-time feedback and support.

3. **Digital Textbooks and E-Books:** Digital textbooks and e-books offer multimedia content, interactive exercises, audio recordings, and video clips to engage learners and reinforce language learning. They provide flexibility in accessing and studying course materials anytime, anywhere, using computers, tablets, or smartphones.

4. **Language Learning Websites and Online Resources:** There are numerous websites and online resources available for language learners, offering

grammar explanations, vocabulary lists, language exercises, audiovisual materials, cultural insights, and authentic language content. Examples include BBC Languages, FluentU, and Linguee.

5. **Language Learning Apps and Games:** Mobile apps and games designed for language learning offer a fun and interactive way to practice language skills on the go. These apps often use gamification techniques, such as rewards, challenges, and leaderboards, to motivate learners and make learning enjoyable. Examples include Memrise, Quizlet, and HelloTalk.

6. **Language Lab Software:** Language lab software provides a virtual environment for language practice and assessment, allowing students to listen to audio recordings, record their own speech, practice pronunciation, and receive feedback from teachers or peers. These tools can be integrated into classroom instruction or used for self-study.

7. **Social Media and Online Communities:** Social media platforms and online communities provide opportunities for language learners to interact with native speakers, join language exchange groups, participate in discussions, and share language learning resources and experiences. Platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Reddit have language-specific groups and forums for learners to connect and practice.

8. **Speech Recognition and Pronunciation Tools:** Speech recognition technology and pronunciation tools help learners improve their speaking and listening skills by providing instant feedback on pronunciation accuracy, intonation, and fluency. These tools can be integrated into language learning apps, virtual classrooms, or standalone software programs.

CONCLUSION

Overall, ICT offers a wide range of tools, resources, and opportunities to support and enhance language teaching and learning. By integrating technology effectively into language instruction, educators can create more engaging, interactive, and personalized learning experiences that meet the diverse needs and preferences of learners.

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